

Low-Cost 3D-Digitalisierung mit SfM in Smartphone Apps

3D-Modelle zum Mitnehmen und Open Data Publikation mit dem Wikiversum und OSM

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3D Tage | 2025 | 04-05 Feb 2025 | Oldenburg | Germany |

04/02/2025

Themenblock: Low Cost

Research Squirrel Engineers Network

DOI [10.5281/zenodo.14789264](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14789264)

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Ich bin **Squilly**, ein IT/3D-interessiertes Eichhörnchen!

Oftmals möchte Squilly (als nicht Geodät)
Gesehenes, “mit nach Hause” nehmen ...

... vieles der Objekte sind auch so, dass sie vergänglich sind ...

Manchmal möchte man auch Kulturerbe “mitnehmen” ...

... und in 3D zu Hause bearbeiten ...

... und mit OSM / Wikidata verknüpfen.

Aber wie macht **Squilly** das?

... und wie verknüpft er das in einem Knowledge Graph?

Gibt es dafür vielleicht SfM Apps mit de Smartphone?

... und freie Kartentools ?

... und Publikationsmöglichkeiten für 3D-Modelle ?

... und Plattformen für Knowledge Graphs?

F A I R

FINDABLE

ACCESSIBLE

INTEROPERABLE

REUSABLE

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via <https://5stardata.info/> and <https://www.w3.org/DesignIssues/LinkedData.html>

Ja! Die Open Source / Open Data und die FAIR-Prinzipien helfen!

2007

2008

2009

2010

2011

2017

2018

2019

2020

2023

Florian Thieri, based on lod-cloud.net, CC BY 4.0, via [Wikimedia Commons](https://commons.wikimedia.org/)

Ziel ist eine verknüpfte *Linked Open Data Cloud* in der (Kulturerbe-Daten) auch 3D-Daten auffindbar und offen sind.

Das Wikiversum und Wikibase Instanzen sind Teil der LOD Cloud

NFDI Humanities MoU Group, CC BY 4.0

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Diese Strukturen sind auch eingebunden in die NFDI

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WIKIBASE

**WIKIBASE
CLOUD**

Sketchfab

Zentral sind hier Community-Hubs und kollaborative Plattformen

KIRI Engine

Auch die digitale low-cost Erfassung mit Structure from Motion (SfM) Technologien ist mit dem Smartphone auch für nicht Geodäten möglich.

SfM-Kampagnen mit der KIRI Engine App

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UCC Stone #1 / CIIC 103 in KIRI ENGINE

Cork: Ogham stone CIIC 81/ UCC 4
3D Model

👍 1 🗨️ 5 ⭐ 0

IN COLLECTIONS

 ogham stones
b-unicycling
👍 13 🗨️ 0

SUGGESTED 3D MODELS

 Cork: Ogham stone CIIC 128/ UCC 25
b-unicycling
👍 5 🗨️ 0 ⭐ 1

 Cork: Ogham stone UCC 12/ CIIC 262
b-unicycling
👍 6 🗨️ 0 ⭐ 0

 Cork: Ogham stone CIIC 127/ UCC 20
b-unicycling
👍 6 🗨️ 0 ⭐ 0

 Cork: Ogham Stone CIIC 89/ UCC 7
b-unicycling
👍 12 🗨️ 0 ⭐ 0

 Cork: Ogham stone CIIC 93/ UCC 8
b-unicycling
👍 10 🗨️ 0 ⭐ 0

 Cork: Ogham stone CIIC 61/ UCC 24
b-unicycling
👍 3 🗨️ 0 ⭐ 0

LOAD MORE

Publikation des UCC Ogham Stone #4 in Sketchfab

Publikation des UCC Ogham Stone #4 in 3DHOP

via <https://www/wiki/AQ2F>

via <https://www/wiki/AQ2F>

via https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:WikiProject_HolyWells

ID	Name	Description
Q112111	St. Peter's Well, County Wick	...
Q112112	St. John's Well, County Wick	...
Q112113	St. James's Well, County Wick	...
Q112114	St. Andrew's Well, County Wick	...
Q112115	St. Patrick's Well, County Wick	...
Q112116	St. Mary's Well, County Wick	...
Q112117	St. Michael's Well, County Wick	...
Q112118	St. Nicholas's Well, County Wick	...
Q112119	St. George's Well, County Wick	...
Q112120	St. David's Well, County Wick	...
Q112121	St. Martin's Well, County Wick	...
Q112122	St. Lawrence's Well, County Wick	...
Q112123	St. Basil's Well, County Wick	...
Q112124	St. Constantine's Well, County Wick	...
Q112125	St. Helena's Well, County Wick	...
Q112126	St. Ursula's Well, County Wick	...
Q112127	St. Agatha's Well, County Wick	...
Q112128	St. Barbara's Well, County Wick	...
Q112129	St. Elizabeth's Well, County Wick	...
Q112130	St. Anne's Well, County Wick	...
Q112131	St. Catherine's Well, County Wick	...
Q112132	St. Margaret's Well, County Wick	...
Q112133	St. Veronica's Well, County Wick	...
Q112134	St. Matilda's Well, County Wick	...
Q112135	St. Gertrude's Well, County Wick	...
Q112136	St. Euphemia's Well, County Wick	...
Q112137	St. Anastasia's Well, County Wick	...
Q112138	St. Cecilia's Well, County Wick	...
Q112139	St. Dymphna's Well, County Wick	...
Q112140	St. Agatha's Well, County Wick	...

The Citizen Science Wikidata Project Holy Wells

Table - 🔍							25 Ergebnisse in 1876 ms	Code	Herunter
item	ItemLabel	img	geo	osm	ed				
Q:121842432	Saint Fiachra's Well		Point(-7.1978959 52.6216672)	8515265450	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/sheastown-st-fiachres-well-low-poly-be3bcd3a3204744a33b2255465028b8>				
Q:126448724	Our Lady's Well		Point(-7.4730101 52.7209032)	8517818852	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/clomanagh-lobermurry-02f647554c604a8b8665ea1bc00f9fd>				
Q:126649228	Lacken Well		Point(-7.2775479 52.5438145)	9886802295	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/garrynamann-lower-lacken-well-d5be9cc7adb4b248c1bb6c2ec542582>				
Q:126487120	St Coleman's Well		Point(-7.2869104 52.7352502)	998532219	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/jenkinson-st-colmans-well-low-poly-fae5988530c648aea73cfd09663954a0>				
Q:122258894	Saint Fiacre's Well		Point(-6.9330041 52.5808599)	8512180854	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/ullard-st-fiachras-well-low-poly-635f79e64b434a6ea08672629bf493d>				
Q:122304309	Saint Molin's Well (Mullennakill)		Point(-7.11584 52.4307541)	8526433151	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/st-molings-well-low-poly-dcfff49b2f3d4348d5cade4f869ad33>				
Q:126456441	Columbkille's Well		Point(-7.0681791 52.4892388)	8513597500	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/inistioge-st-columbkills-well-low-poly-b0845424e49d40cfa4f0437c698ac7f5>				
Q:126454844	Lady's Well		Point(-6.9566958 52.5411618)	8513574146	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/grauguenamanagh-ladys-well-9ed7bcf22e184897a5b8e758cef7249e>				
Q:114439798	Kenny's Well		Point(-7.26219 52.65325)	1158290017	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/kennys-well-indoors-low-poly-685c7b9d3b0e4ba09e22263342cfc3>				
Q:126458702	St. Nicholas's Well (Killamery)		Point(-7.4459883 52.4752746)	6167966637	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/killamery-st-nicholas-well-low-poly-0eeb400854164819afc5bae58dff8da>				
Q:126456487	Well of the Festival		Point(-7.1257749 52.4660232)	8518908237	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/powerswood-tobernalia-ee33390870b4d9886a0bb3c42029df69>				
Q:126456487	Well of the Festival		Point(-7.1257749 52.4660232)	8518908237	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/powerswood-tobernalia-ee33390870b4d9886a0bb3c42029df69>				
Q:129263926	Holy Well		Point(-7.1637296 52.5134682)	7673751375	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/newtown-jeipoint-st-nicholas-well-62521654a1ec40c7403ccbf448869>				
Q:126374490	Trinity Well		Point(-7.2710769 52.7262158)	11942593399	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/ballyraffon-trinity-well-553073f9100040e789890d3edd3cd851>				
Q:122302608	St. Kieran's Well		Point(-7.3800887 52.3975027)	10544065862	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/whitechurch-kilkieran-st-kierans-well-8cdea3b21314508eb7b69faca418d76>				
Q:121840779	St. Lachtain's Well		Point(-7.38951 52.7316)		<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/freshford-st-lachtains-well-low-poly-ae1ef14daa74d33bb076407134e81e>				
Q:122258906	Lady's Well		Point(-7.0093773 52.6293381)	8513439301	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/goresbridge-ladys-well-status-low-poly-b6dctfdcece3e4f6ab15a3ad6550c2d18>				
Q:122258906	Lady's Well		Point(-7.0093773 52.6293381)	8513439301	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/goresbridge-ladys-well-status-low-poly-b6dctfdcece3e4f6ab15a3ad6550c2d18>				
Q:122258906	Lady's Well		Point(-7.0093773 52.6293381)	8513439301	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/goresbridge-ladys-well-status-low-poly-b6dctfdcece3e4f6ab15a3ad6550c2d18>				
Q:122189562	Saint Augustine's Well		Point(-7.38765 52.54522)		<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/callan-st-augustines-well-low-poly-9feacac0fda14a189a1a59d2e123b1e4>				
Q:126456468	Holy Cross well		Point(-7.0437511 52.4878257)	8514375323	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/kilcross-holy-cross-well-low-poly-ca165580c28429392b1a06491333148>				
Q:126657210	St. David's Well		Point(-7.2979334 52.6195581)	12144379129	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/castleinch-st-davids-well-4b6eae78a6cc43c2aee79bb6ab7c69a8>				
Q:126918993	Kilkeasy Holy Well		Point(-7.2246427 52.4410735)	12015630647	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/kilkeasy-holy-well-67a39daeb3c54539a8a3147ecb29f3f67>				
Q:126487358	St Brigid's Well		Point(-7.3565632 52.6115585)	8517798092	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/toberbreedia-st-brigids-well-56e71b0735fc4f17bdf36b4c5b2a12a7>				
Q:126454422	St Leonard's Well		Point(-7.2955635 52.5006254)	7412516778	<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/st-leonards-well-c6e89f2e2ae147ba90553a3a16fda690>				

Holy Wells mit Sketchfab Links zu 3D-Modellen (01.02.2025)

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Anne-Karoline Distel, CC0, via Wikimedia Commons

Freshford: St Lachtain's Well

via <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q121840779>

Wikidata

Item: **Toberlachtain** (Q121840779)

Holy well dedicated to St. Lachtain near Freshford, Co. Kilderry

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	Toberlachtain	Holy well dedicated to St. Lachtain near Freshford, Co. Kilderry	Tober Lachtain St. Lachtain's Well Toberlachtain
German	No label (draft)	No description (draft)	
Russian	No label (draft)	No description (draft)	
Ancient English	No label (draft)	No description (draft)	

Statements

- instance of: holy well (1 reference)
- Holy Well Semantic Concept (0 references)
- spring (3 references)
- holy well (1 reference)
- status of use: abandoned (1 reference)

Identifiers

- Irish Sites and Monuments Record ID**: KK013-025---- (1 reference)
- OpenStreetMap way ID**: 935503837 (0 references)

Image: Toberlachtain Holy Lachtain Well, 3.08k x 2.00k, 3.54 MB (0 references)

Names: Lachtain near Freshford (0 references)

Country: Ireland (0 references)

Location: County Kilderry (0 references), Freshford (0 references)

OpenStreetMap | Bearbeiten | Chronik | Export

Suchen:

Weg: Saint Lachtain's Well (935503837)

Version #7
added sketchfab link

Bearbeitet vor 3 Monaten von bruncycling
Änderungssatz #15259797

Tags

alt_name	Toberlachtain
amenity	place_of_worship
check_date	2023-08-25
denomination	roman_catholic
description	Walled enclosure with wrought iron gate. Stone paved ground with subterranean water basin which is covered in water lenses.
name	Toberlachtain
name:en	Saint Lachtain's Well
name:etymological:wikidata	Q118774069
name:ga	Tober Lachtain
natural	spring
place_of_worship	holy_well
ref:Edm	KK013-025
religion	christian
source	British War Office mapsurvey

via <https://www.openstreetmap.org/way/935503837>

Freshford: St Lachtain's Well

<https://squirrelbase.wikibase.cloud>

Objekte sind referenzierbar über die Wikibase **squirrelbase**

Kulturgut

**Adlerstein und Kolossalstatue
Konstantins des Großen**

Florian Thiery, CC BY 4.0

Florian Thiery, CC BY 4.0

Open Street Map Mitwirkende, ODbL

Auf dem Weg Vorbei in Aachen am Dreiländerpunkt ...

“138 Adlersteine markierten als mittelalterliche Grenzsteine einst die Grenzen des Aachener Reichs. Von denen sind maximal noch 18 Steine zu finden, manche demoliert und unleserlich.” Quelle: Wikimedia Commons (<https://w.wiki/AmoM>)

... entdeckt man den Adlerstein

via <https://www.openstreetmap.org/node/1128569466>

OpenStreetMap Bearbeiten Chronik Export

Suchen Wo ist das?

Knoten: Adlerstein (1128569466)

Version #8
change image

Bearbeitet vor etwa einem Monat von fthiergeo
Änderungssatz #154519289
Standort: 50.7617299, 6.0187331

Tags

description	No. 16 am Schorenkopf
historic	boundary_stone
image	File:Adlerstein_Aachen_Vaals.jpg
name	Adlerstein
urtsketchfab	https://skfb.ly/p6nO9
website	https://grenzsteine.de/530599968a1463356/0342949925132eF01/index.html
wikimedia_commons	Category:Grenssteen achter Wilhelminatoren, Vaals

XML herunterladen

« Version #1 - Verlauf anzeigen - Version #8 »

Adlerstein in Vaals (Niederlande) in OSM

Main page
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Item Discussion

Boundary stone with eagle (Q17445038)

monument in Vaals, Netherlands [edit](#)

→ In more languages

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	Boundary stone with eagle	monument in Vaals, Netherlands	
German	Adlerstein Grenzstein (Aachen)	Vaals, Netherlands	Adlerstein am Vaalser Berg (So...
Italian	No label defined	No description defined	
American English	No label defined	No description defined	

All entered languages

Statements

instance of	boundary marker	edit
	0 references	+ add reference
	monolith	edit
	0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value

image [edit](#)

Vaals-Grenssteen achter Wilhelmintoren (1).JPG
3,000 × 4,000, 4.11 MB

point in time 22 November 2010

0 references [+ add reference](#) [+ add value](#)

country	Netherlands	edit
	0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value

located in the administrative territorial entity	Vaals	edit
	0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value

located on street	Vaargrenzeberg	edit
	0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value

location	Vaals	edit
	0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value

located in/on physical feature	Vaalserberg	edit
	0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value

coordinate location [edit](#)

50°45′44″N, 0°17′E

0 references [+ add reference](#) [+ add value](#)

heritage designation	Rijksmonument	edit
	start time 23 January 1907	
	1 reference	
		+ add value

street address	aan de NL-DE-grens achter de Wilhelmintoren op de Vaalserberg (Dutch)	edit
	0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value

Commons category	Grenssteen achter Wilhelmintoren, Vaals	edit
	0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value

Identifiers

Rijksmonument ID	30638	edit
	0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value

OpenStreetMap node ID	112850400	edit
	0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value

Adlerstein in Vaals (Niederlande) in Wikidata

Florian Thiery, CC BY 4.0, via <https://skfb.ly/n6n09>

via <http://archaeosquirrels.cloud/?model=NLRMR-36638>

Adlerstein in Vaals (Niederlande) in Sketchfab / 3DHOP

Adlerstein in Vaals (Niederlande) (Q5)

object ✎ edit

▸ in more languages

Statements

instance of	Object	✎ edit
	- 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value
KIRI URL	https://www.kiriengine.app/share/ShareMode?code=Q7ZGH4&size=doc6715b0a51441988848b71f7bb0562	✎ edit
	- 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value
Wikidata Q-ID	Q17445038	✎ edit
	- 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value
OSM ID	node/1128569466	✎ edit
	- 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value
geometry	50°45'42.2276"N, 6°17.4392"E	✎ edit
	- 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value
3DCHIP URL	http://archaeosquirrelis.cloud/?mode=NLRMR-36038	✎ edit
	- 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value
Sketchfab URL	https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/adlerstein-grenzstein-in-aachen-ca827c32825c44f9ba1f6ca178e5519b	✎ edit
	- 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value

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Adlerstein in Vaals (Niederlande) Q5

Bilder: Florian Thiery, CC BY 4.0

Kolossalstatue Konstantins des Großen

3D-Modelle zum "Puzzeln"

via http://archaeosquirrels.cloud/?model=Rom_Capitol_KopfKonstantin

via http://archaeosquirrels.cloud/?model=Rom_Capitol_HandKonstantin

via http://archaeosquirrels.cloud/?model=Rom_Capitol_FussKonstantin

3D-Modelle in 3DHOP

© Irene Gaumé for Factum Foundation

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Florian Thiery, CC BY 4.0

3D-Modelle zum "Puzzeln"

via <https://squirrelbase.wikibase.cloud/entity/Q6>

Item Discussion

Rom Capitol Kopf Konstantin ^(Q6)

object edit

+ In more languages

Statements

instance of	Object	edit
	- 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value

KIRI URL	https://www.kiriengine.app/share/ShareMode?code=G7ZG14&serialize=9b02a50b245028559acc0a3a642c	edit
	- 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value

Wikidata Q-ID	Q1289781	edit
	- 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value

OSM ID	relation/9609127	edit
	- 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value

geometry	41°53'34.452"N, 12°28'57.122"E	edit
	- 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value

3DHOP URL	http://archaeosquirrels.cloud/?model=Rom_Capitol_KopfKonstantin	edit
	- 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value

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In other languages

+ Add links

Item Discussion

Rom Capitol Hand Konstantin ^(Q7)

object edit

+ In more languages

Statements

instance of	Object	edit
	- 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value

KIRI URL	https://www.kiriengine.app/share/ShareMode?code=G7ZG14&serialize=2d505c654c460eb20e8e62d9770c	edit
	- 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value

Wikidata Q-ID	Q1289781	edit
	- 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value

OSM ID	relation/9609127	edit
	- 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value

geometry	41°53'34.4520"N, 12°28'57.1220"E	edit
	- 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value

3DHOP URL	http://archaeosquirrels.cloud/?model=Rom_Capitol_HandKonstantin	edit
	- 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value

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In other languages

+ Add links

via <https://squirrelbase.wikibase.cloud/entity/Q7>

Item Discussion

Rom Capitol Fuß Konstantin ^(Q8)

object edit

+ In more languages

Statements

instance of	Object	edit
	- 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value

KIRI URL	https://www.kiriengine.app/share/ShareMode?code=G7ZG14&serialize=09bc1011b8043e794bab40b020c487	edit
	- 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value

Wikidata Q-ID	Q1289781	edit
	- 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value

OSM ID	relation/9609127	edit
	- 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value

geometry	41°53'34.452"N, 12°28'57.122"E	edit
	- 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value

3DHOP URL	http://archaeosquirrels.cloud/?model=Rom_Capitol_FussKonstantin	edit
	- 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value

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In other languages

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Rom Capitol Konstantin Kopf/Hand/Fuß **Q6/7/8**

Heritage & Kultur

Quer durch die Republik ...

Asymmetrische Vase (Berlin Ku'damm)

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Item Discussion

Asymmetrische Vase (Berlin Ku'damm) (Q4)

object

edit

[In more languages](#)

Statements

instance of	Object - 0 references + add reference + add value
KIRI URL	https://www.kiriengine.app/share/ShareModel?code=G7ZGI4&serialize=aa18edf1cd19494a803d620286cc0888 - 0 references + add reference + add value
Wikidata Q-ID	Q116206915 - 0 references + add reference + add value
OSM ID	node/2554278342 - 0 references + add reference + add value
geometry	52°30′9.6282″N, 13°19′29.9561″E - 0 references + add reference + add value

Asymmetrische Vase (Berlin Ku'damm) **Q4**

Berliner Siegestsäule (Mosaik)

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Berliner Siegestsäule (Mosaik) (Q9)

object

In more languages

Statements

instance of	Q9 Object	
	0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value
KIRI URL	Q9 https://www.kiriengine.app/share/ShareModel?code=G7ZG14&serialize=0d732429296e4131b33525ffc8267214	
	0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value
Wikidata Q-ID	Q9 Q154987	
	0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value
OSM ID	Q9 way/718035022	
	0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value
geomety	Q9 52°30′52.243″N, 13°21′0.389″E	
	0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value

Asymmetrische Vase (Berlin Ku'damm) **Q9**

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Der "Große Sitzende" (Dom Würzburg)

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Der "Große Sitzende" (Dom Würzburg) (Q10)

object

edit

» In more languages

Statements

instance of	Object	edit
	~ 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value

KIRI URL	https://www.kirienline.app/share/ShareModel?code=G7ZGI4&serialize=4dbec790594c4527803b6b68975af2e9	edit
	~ 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value

OSM ID	node/9893293767	edit
	~ 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value

geometry	49°47′37.0907″N, 9°55′54.7151″E	edit
	~ 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value

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Der "Große Sitzende" (Dom Würzburg) Q10

Gedenkstein von Kurfürst Karl (Schloss Heidelberg)

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Gedenkstein von Kurfürst Karl (Schloss Heidelberg) (Q11)

object

[edit](#)

[In more languages](#)

Statements

instance of	Object	edit
	- 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value
KIRI URL	https://www.kiriengine.app/share/ShareModel?code=G7ZGI4&serialize=2f2a937b3cff49c49c0940de4786de8e	edit
	- 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value
Wikidata Q-ID	Q327265	edit
	- 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value
OSM ID	way/254154168	edit
	- 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value
geometry	49°24′38.045″N, 8°42′50.558″E	edit
	- 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value

Gedenkstein von Kurfürst Karl (Schloss Heidelberg) **Q11**

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Vater Rhein (Schloss Heidelberg)

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Item Discussion

Vater Rhein (Schloss Heidelberg) (Q12)

object

edit

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Statements

instance of	Object - 0 references	edit + add reference + add value
KIRI URL	https://www.kiriengine.app/share/ShareModel?code=G7ZGI4&serialize=59a4cb4eba14242972cfa2d9f76fbaa - 0 references	edit + add reference + add value
Wikidata Q-ID	Q131632857 - 0 references	edit + add reference + add value
OSM ID	node/1899287777 - 0 references	edit + add reference + add value
geometry	49°24′36.8921″N, 8°43′8.8928″E - 0 references	edit + add reference + add value

Vater Rhein (Schloss Heidelberg) **Q12**

Domnapf (Speyer)

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Item Discussion

Domnapf (Speyer) (Q13)

object

[edit](#)

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Statements

instance of	Object	edit
	- 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value
KIRI URL	https://www.kiriengine.app/share/ShareModel?code=G7ZG14&serialize=782ce7cb17794cc6bcc85796ee503b7b	edit
	- 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value
Wikidata Q-ID	Q22627	edit
	- 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value
OSM ID	way/150902024	edit
	- 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value
geometry	49°19′2.161″N, 8°26′28.316″E	edit
	- 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value

Domnapf (Speyer) Q13

Geißbockbrunnen (Deidesheim)

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Geißbockbrunnen (Deidesheim) (Q14)

object

In more languages

Statements

instance of	Object	edit
	0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value
KIRI URL	https://www.kiriengine.app/share/ShareModel?code=G7ZGI4&serialize=ae936fda6b4763b47cbc594f8fead2	edit
	0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value
Wikidata Q-ID	Q122573616	edit
	0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value
OSM ID	way/1314789890	edit
	0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value
geometry	49°24'27.202"N, 8°11'26.149"E	edit
	0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value

Geißbockbrunnen (Deidesheim) **Q14**

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Köln Hohenzollernbrücke (Schlösser)

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Köln Hohenzollernbrücke (Schlösser) (Q15)

object

edit

In more languages

Statements

instance of	Object	edit
	0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value

KIRI URL	https://www.kiriengine.app/share/ShareModel?code=G7ZG4&serialize=a8bad77d56304d669751159015997b2f	edit
	0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value

Wikidata Q-ID	Q696762	edit
	0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value

OSM ID	way/268130024	edit
	0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value

geometry	50°56'29.116"N, 6°57'57.398"E	edit
	0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value

Köln Hohenzollernbrücke (Schlösser) Q15

“Vergängliche” Objekte

Beispiele aus den südtiroler Dolomiten

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Mimi - Domenica Palamara geb. Spunti di Viaggio, CC BY

Florian Thiery, CC BY 4.0

Statua del Mendicante di Anterselva

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Statua del Mendicante di Anterselva (Q16)

object

[edit](#)

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Statements

instance of	Object	edit
	0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value
KIRI URL	<code>https://www.kiriengine.app/share/ShareModel?code=G7ZGI4&serialize=6a4052cbe9ec4924954073f1ea13355e</code>	edit
	0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value
Wikidata Q-ID	Q572562	edit
	0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value
OSM ID	node/12549447475	edit
	0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value
geometry	<code>46°52'57.1336"N, 12°10'4.5131"E</code>	edit
	0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value

Statua del Mendicante di Anterselva **Q16**

Schneemann in St. Magdalena (Gsies)

Item [Discussion](#)

Schneemann in St. Magdalena (Gsies) (Q18)

temporal object edit

[In more languages](#)

Statements

instance of	<div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 5px;"> temporal Object edit <div style="text-align: center; margin-top: 5px;"> 0 references </div> </div> <div style="text-align: right; background-color: #e0e0e0; padding: 5px;"> + add reference + add value </div>
KIRI URL	<div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 5px;"> https://www.kiriengine.app/share/ShareModel?code=G7ZGI4&serialize=f784a11993b745669f5d73685c7685f8 edit <div style="text-align: center; margin-top: 5px;"> 0 references </div> </div> <div style="text-align: right; background-color: #e0e0e0; padding: 5px;"> + add reference + add value </div>
geometry	<div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 5px;"> 46°51'8.294"N, 12°14'53.135"E edit <div style="text-align: center; margin-top: 5px;"> 0 references </div> </div> <div style="text-align: right; background-color: #e0e0e0; padding: 5px;"> + add reference + add value </div>

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Schneemann in St. Magdalena (Gsies) **Q18**

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Schneemann am Dreizinnenblick

Item [Discussion](#)

Schneemann am Dreizinnenblick (Q19)

temporal object

edit

[In more languages](#)

Statements

instance of	temporal Object edit
	~ 0 references
	+ add reference
+ add value	

KIRI URL	https://www.kiriengine.app/share/ShareModel?code=GZGI4&serialize=69b0d37d948847b7991a7920dd9ec98f edit
	~ 0 references
	+ add reference
+ add value	

OSM ID	node/279714434 edit
	~ 0 references
	+ add reference
+ add value	

geometry	46°38'17.3180"N, 12°14'3.6154"E edit
	~ 0 references
	+ add reference
+ add value	

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Schneemann am Dreizinnenblick **Q19**

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Eismännchen auf dem Pragser Wildsee

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Eismännchen auf dem Pragser Wildsee (Q20)

temporal object

[edit](#)

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Statements

instance of	temporal Object	edit
	- 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value
KIRI URL	https://www.kiriengine.app/share/ShareModel?code=G7ZGI4&serialize=2c3aa8f0980f475697c1fe01ac13b828	edit
	- 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value
OSM ID	relation/14517899	edit
	- 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value
Wikidata Q-ID	Q445369	edit
	- 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value
geometry	46°41'48.1114"N, 12°5'1.7318"E	edit
	- 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value

Eismännchen auf dem Pragser Wildsee **Q20**

Eismännchen auf Stein auf dem Pragser Wildsee

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Eismännchen auf Stein auf dem Pragser Wildsee (Q21)

temporal object

edit

[In more languages](#)

Statements

instance of	temporal Object	edit
	- 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value
KIRI URL	https://www.kiriengine.app/share/ShareModel?code=G7ZG14&serialize=ae53941ea80744668b8fe9dd133a745b	edit
	- 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value
OSM ID	relation/14517899	edit
	- 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value
Wikidata Q-ID	Q445369	edit
	- 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value
geometry	46°41'48.1114"N, 12°5'1.7318"E	edit
	- 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value

Eismännchen auf Stein auf dem Pragser Wildsee **Q21**

Squilly hat es geschafft!

Finis! Thx!

Questions?

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